

OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES

Psychologically and Physiologically Impact of COVID-19 on Students Who Studying in China and Stocked in Pakistan (A Cross-Sectional Study)

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ABSTRACT

Background: The Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has brought destructive consequences on the global political, economical, social, financial, and healthcare structures [1]. The pandemic has risen up the level of anxiety, depressive thoughts and psychological stress among students who were studying in china, but now stocked in home country. Approximately 30,000 Pakistani students are being enrolled in M.Phil and PhD in China. The aim of this study is to identify the psychological and physiological impact of COVID-19 on these students.

Method: The cross-sectional study has been adopted via web-based platform for students who are studying in different institutions of China but now stoked in Pakistan due to pandemic. Questionnaire has been developed via Google Survey form which were distributed through social media like WeChat, Facebook. The purpose of this study is to assess depression, anxiety and sources of distress [2].

Result: This survey was conducted in December 2020, in which 1300 students took part (700 Phd and M.phil related while 500 Medical and Engineering). Majority of students are male (84.1%) and few females (13.9%). The result shows that students who have moderate-severe anxiety and depression about their graduation (score ≥ 12) were 75% and 25%, respectively.

Conclusion: The severely affected students from this pandemic are from the Phd, M.phil research related students.

References

1. Alkhamees AA, Alrashed SA, Alzunaydi AA, Almohimeed AS, Aljohani MS. The psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the general population of Saudi Arabia. *Compr Psychiatry*. 2020 Oct;102:152192. doi: 10.1016/j.comppsy.2020.152192. Epub 2020 Jul 12. PMID: 32688022; PMCID: PMC7354380.
2. Leonardo Villani, Roberta Pastorino, Enrico Molinari, Franco Anelli, Walter Ricciardi, Guendalina Graffigna, Stefania Boccia. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on psychological well-being of students in an Italian university: A web-based crosssectional survey. 2021;17:39. doi: 10.1186/s12992-021-00680-w.

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